

ANALYSIS OF ARCHIVAL SOURCES ON THE HISTORY OF CUSTOMS BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT IN TURKESTAN

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Abstract: In this article, the author analyzes funds and archival sources related to the history of customs business in Turkestan in the 19th – early 20th centuries. Critical analysis of historical events and facts based on objective scientific methods is of crucial importance.

This analysis should not be limited to a superficial glance, but should include an in-depth study of sources, a thorough examination of information and consideration of the context. Archival work, the basis of historical knowledge, plays a huge role here. The effectiveness of working with historical heritage directly depends on the organization and activities of archival institutions. Modern archives are not only document repositories, but also information centers that are actively introducing digital technologies. It should be noted that a critical analysis of historical sources involves not only studying the documents themselves, but also analyzing the methods of their creation, taking into account possible distortions and inaccuracies. Researchers must have critical thinking skills and the ability to distinguish facts from interpretations. Only this approach allows us to objectively understand the past and learn useful lessons from it for the present and the future. A systematic approach to archival work, modern technologies and highly professional qualifications of archival workers are prerequisites for the effective use of historical experience.

Key words: archive, fund, customs, sources, zakat institutions, customs district, duties.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada muallif 19-asr – 20-asr boshlarida Turkistonda bojxona ishlarining o‘rganish tarixiga oid fondlar va arxiv manbalarini tahlil qiladi. Tarixiy voqea va faktlarni ob‘ektiv ilmiy uslublar asosida tanqidiy tahlil qilish hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega.

Ushbu tahlil faqat yuzaki qarash bilan cheklanmasligi kerak, balki manbalarni chuqur o‘rganish, ma’lumotni sinchkovlik bilan tekshirish va kontekstni ko‘rib chiqishni o‘z ichiga olishi kerak. Bu yerda tarixiy bilimlarning asosi bo‘lgan arxiv ishi juda katta rol o‘ynaydi. Tarixiy meros bilan ishlash samaradorligi bevosita arxiv muassasalarining tashkil etilishi va faoliyatiga bog‘liq. Zamonaviy arxivlar nafaqat hujjatlar ombori, balki raqamli texnologiyalarni faol joriy etuvchi axborot markazlaridir. Shuni ta’kidlash kerakki, tarixiy manbalarni tanqidiy tahlil qilish nafaqat hujjatlarning o‘zini o‘rganishni, balki mumkin bo‘lgan buzilishlar va noaniqliklarni hisobga olgan holda ularni yaratish usullarini tahlil qilishni ham o‘z ichiga oladi. Tadqiqotchilar tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatiga va faktlarni talqinlardan ajrata olish qobiliyatiga ega bo‘lishi kerak. Faqat ana shunday yondashuv o‘tmishni xolisona anglab, undan bugun va kelajak uchun foydali saboqlar chiqarish imkonini beradi. Arxiv ishiga tizimli yondashish, zamonaviy texnologiyalar va arxiv xodimlarining yuqori kasbiy malakasi tarixiy tajribadan samarali foydalanishning zarur shartidir.

Tayanch so‘zlar: arxiv, fond, bojxona, manbalar, zakot muassasalari, bojxona okrugi, bojlar.

Аннотация: в данной статье автором анализируются фонды и архивные источники касающихся истории изучения таможенного дела в Туркестане XIX – начала XX веков. Критический анализ исторических событий и фактов на основе объективных научных методов имеет решающее значение.

Этот анализ не должен ограничиваться поверхностным взглядом, а должен включать глубокое изучение источников, тщательное изучение информации и рассмотрение контекста. Огромную роль здесь играет архивное дело — основа исторических знаний. Эффективность работы с историческим наследием напрямую зависит от организации и деятельности архивных учреждений. Современные архивы — это не только хранилища документов, но и информационные центры, активно внедряющие цифровые технологии. Следует отметить, что критический анализ исторических источников

предполагает не только изучение самих документов, но и анализ методики их создания с учетом возможных искажений и неточностей. Исследователи должны обладать навыками критического мышления и способностью отличать факты от интерпретаций. Только такой подход позволяет нам объективно понять прошлое и извлечь из него полезные уроки для настоящего и будущего. Системный подход к архивному делу, современные технологии и высокая профессиональная квалификация архивных работников являются необходимыми условиями эффективного использования исторического опыта.

Ключевые слова: архив, фонд, таможня, источники, закятные учреждения, таможенный округ, пошлины.

Introduction

The increasing attention of society to the knowledge of the historical past puts forward the need to create theoretical and methodological foundations of national history. The solution to this problem is connected not only with the revision of ideological ideas and conceptual approaches, but also with the expansion of the information base of historical research, the study, critical analysis and introduction into scientific circulation of new historical sources, their objective interpretation in accordance with the requirements of modern source studies.

At a meeting with historians, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan spoke about the need for an objective and honest study of history in conditions of independence, emphasizing that the people of Uzbekistan are the creators of their own history, the bearer of an original national culture and a rich historical past [1.].

The cultural values of the peoples of Uzbekistan and its spiritual heritage have served as a powerful source of spirituality for many millennia. No society can build its perspective without promoting and preserving historical values.

Modern social development is directly related to the knowledge of historical experience. In this regard, a critical analysis and scientific assessment of the past is required based on an objective study of socially significant events and historical facts. In this sense, it is of fundamental importance to analyze the organization of archival work, to study the activities of the leading archival institutions of the Republic aimed at acquiring valuable historical sources.

The current level of historical science and the importance of its tasks dictate the need to equip historians with methods of scientific research, including working with numerous and diverse archival sources. In this sense, it is of great scientific importance to inform historians about the availability, content and significance of archival materials covering the history of customs in Turkestan at the end of the 19th – 20th century.

Problem statement

It is known that with the conquest of Central Asia by the Russian Empire, a new administrative management system was introduced, which played a huge role in using the natural and economic resources of the region in its interests. A certain part of economic income was made up of duties from foreign trade. Initially, control over the import and export of goods was retained by zakyat institutions [2. 248.]. This was due, on the one

hand, to the caution of the imperial authorities in reforming the existing regional order, on the other, to considerations of providing, as far as possible, greater benefits to Russian merchants. However, the decrease in revenue from customs duties and the development of smuggling caused discontent among the ruling circles, as a result of which, since 1886, customs institutions subordinate to the Ministry of Finance of the Russian Empire have been established in the Turkestan General Government.

The activities of the imperial administrative apparatus in this regard have been fully reflected in numerous written sources stored in the National Archives of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The vast majority of them relate to materials of a regulatory and executive nature.

Research methods

In the process of studying and analyzing this article, historical research methods were used. These include approaches such as analysis, synthesis, generalization, comparison, as well as methods of hypotheses and analogies, deduction and induction, along with others. Special methods are tools adapted to the requirements and needs of a particular science. In particular, the methods of historical research include chronological, historical-comparative, and others.

Results and examples

The group of regulatory sources includes laws, regulations, instructions, and rules for the introduction of customs in Turkestan. If the regulations on the administration of the region contain information on the management procedure and the system of administrative institutions of the region, then the laws reflect government measures to establish or reorganize customs supervision.

For example, Collection No. 58 of the Collection of Laws of the Russian Empire contains the Law of May 2, 1886 «On the establishment of a customs unit in the Turkestan Region». The study of this law provides an opportunity for the researcher to familiarize himself with the official rights and duties of an official of special assignments of the Ministry of Finance for Customs Affairs, the staff of customs institutions of Turkestan, and the procedure for allocating funds for their maintenance. It should be emphasized that for the development of customs in Turkestan, a number of legislative acts were issued, included in special collections of laws and regulations on customs in Central Asia, published in 1911 and 1914.

Thus, in the collection published in 1911, the documents are divided into seven sections according to their content. The first section «Organization of customs supervision» contains legislative acts on the organization of customs supervision in Central Asia. In turn, it is divided into three parts of documents covering issues of customs administration, staff of customs administration and customs agencies, and border protection [3. 1-32].

The second section, «Customs Tariffs», includes tariffs and rules for imported and exported goods, and orders on the collection of duties [3. 33-60].

The third section, «Customs production», contains the rules of customs production, on the transportation and inspection of goods, orders for the passage of goods, on preferential passage of goods for the Emir of Bukhara and the government of Persia, on the folding of goods and folding fees, on the passage of printed

works, customs books, sanitary measures and medical assistance to customs officials, penalties for smuggling and violation of Customs regulations [61-126].

The fourth department, «On the export of Russian goods abroad with a refund of duty», contains lists of customs offices, general orders for the export and re-import of manufactures, and rules for the admission of credit receipts by State Bank institutions and treasuries [3. 127-142].

The fifth section, «On the export of Russian goods abroad with exemption from excise duty», contains lists of institutions exempt from excise duty, general orders for the export of credit receipts, and the procedure for the export and re-import of excise goods [3. 143-164].

The sixth section «On the passage of parcels and written correspondence» includes legal documents on the passage of parcels and written correspondence from Central Asia to Russia and vice versa [3. 165-174].

The seventh section «On the transit of foreign goods» highlights the transit pass procedures, presented by the orders and rules. In addition, the texts of job descriptions of customs officials are provided as appendices [3. 181-246].

A group of official sources of an executive nature, which provides a summary of information on all aspects of the development of customs institutions and illuminating the essence of the customs policy of the Russian Empire in Turkestan, is concentrated in the following funds of the National Archive of Uzbekistan: Tashkent Customs Inspection Site or Turkestan Customs District [4]; Customs inspectors of the I-IV sections of the Turkestan Customs District [5]; Samarkand [6] and Kokand [7] customs. Conditionally, according to the content, the documents can be divided into the following categories: annual official reports of the regional colonial administration on customs affairs of Turkestan; annual reports of the heads of regional customs; customs inspectors of the I-IV sections of the Turkestan customs district; report of the audit commission prepared under the leadership of K.K. Palen; statistical appendices to reports and surveys on the regions of Turkestan. They were compiled either in handwritten or printed form.

As an example of such a source, we can cite the report on the situation of the Turkestan Customs District with data from surveys of institutions of the First and second sections, compiled by the head of the district R.Gubarevich-Radobylskiy in March 1904 and submitted to the Department of Customs Duties of the Russian Empire [8]. It provides a detailed description of the activities of the First and second customs sections and institutions, information on the procedure for collecting duties, income received, import and export of goods, the course of combating smuggling and the methods used in its transportation, border control, etc.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can clarify that the National Archives of Uzbekistan contains a significant volume of unique documents, organized in chronological order and reflecting the entire picture of customs affairs in Turkestan in the late 19th – early 20th centuries. An analysis of the historiography and source studies of this problem shows that these materials have not yet been sufficiently studied. The study and introduction of these sources into scientific circulation will help to more accurately reveal the essence of the customs policy of the Russian Empire and the state of customs affairs in Turkestan in the period under study.

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